

Enhanced photorefractivity and rare-earth photoluminescence in SnO₂ nanocrystals-based photonic glass-ceramics

Thi Ngoc Lam Tran^{1,2,3,*}, Anna Szczurek¹, Stefano Varas¹, Cristina Armellini¹, Alessandro Carpentiero¹, Andrea Chiappini¹, Erica Iacob⁴, Gloria Ischia⁵, Simone Berneschi⁶, Gualtiero Nunzi Conti⁶, Monica Bollani⁷, Francesco Scotognella^{2,8}, Giancarlo C. Righini⁶, Paweł Gluchowski⁹, Alessandro Chiasera¹, Anna Lukowiak⁹, Maurizio Ferrari¹

¹IFN-CNR CSMFO Lab. and FBK Photonics Unit, Via alla Cascata 56/C, 38123 Povo, Italy;

²Department of Physics, Politecnico di Milano, Piazza Leonardo da Vinci 32, 20133 Milano, Italy;

³Department of Materials Technology, Faculty of Applied Science, Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology and Education, Vo Van Ngan Street 1, Thu Duc District, 720214 Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam;

⁴Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Sensors and Devices, Micro Nano Facility, Via Sommarive 18, Povo, Trento, 38123, Italy;

⁵Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Trento, Via Sommarive 9, Povo, Trento, 38123, Italy;

⁶MiPLab, IFAC-CNR, Via Madonna del Piano 10, 50019 Sesto Fiorentino, Italy;

⁷CNR-IFN, P.zza Leonardo da Vinci 32, Milano, 20133 Italy;

⁸Center for Nano Science and Technology@PoliMi, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT), Via Giovanni Pascoli, 70/3, 20133, Milan, Italy;

⁹Institute of Low Temperature and Structure Research, PAS, ul. Okólna 2, 50422 Wrocław, Poland;

Abstract. This work presents state of the art rare-earth activated SnO₂ nanocrystals - based transparent glass-ceramics. With combined enhancements in both photorefractivity and rare-earth photoluminescence, the glass-ceramic has unique benefits as a lasing material. It exhibits high photorefractivity with UV induced refractive index modifications in the order of 10⁻³. Exploiting its high photorefractivity, optical gratings are fabricated on the glass-ceramic under an energy-efficient direct UV writing process. Furthermore, SnO₂ semiconductor nanocrystals are also employed as efficient rare-earth sensitizers enhancing drastically the rare-earth photoluminescence.

1 Introduction

Optical materials and photonic structures are strategic for many applications, e.g., sensing, integrated photonics, light sources, quantum technologies, and green energy systems. Such research activities pave the way for tackling current challenges, opening new scientific knowledge and technological advancements. To design and tailor various interesting functionalities, nanocomposites are among the more appealing materials. Transparent glass-ceramic are two-phases systems constituted by nanocrystals distributed in a glass matrix [1,2]. When the nanocrystals are activated with rare earth ions, photonic glass-ceramics exhibit unique properties such as [1,3](i) the high absorption and emission cross-sections, (ii) the reduction of the non-radiative relaxation processes thanks to the lower phonon cut-off energy, and (iii) the tailoring of the ion-ion interaction by the control of the rare-earth ion partition[3]. Furthermore, the desired properties can be tuned on the base of composition, material, and respective volume fractions of crystalline and amorphous phases.

In this work, Er³⁺-activated SiO₂-SnO₂ glass-ceramics are discussed. This system uniquely merges two interesting properties: (i) high photorefractivity, and (ii) SnO₂ nanocrystals act as efficient rare-earth luminescent sensitizers. Therefore, this photorefractive glass-ceramic can settle the issue of rare-earths' low absorption cross-section. Furthermore, it can provide strategic fabrication approach for defining channel waveguides and optical gratings with minimal losses using direct UV writing technique[4-6].

2 Sol-gel derived SnO₂ nanocrystals-based photonic glass-ceramics

SnO₂-doped glasses and glass-ceramics can be fabricated by several techniques [7-11]. However, issues of SnO₂ volatilization during the high temperature preparation [9], or α -Sn nanoclusters and nonstoichiometric SnO_x nanoparticles [12,13] raised a challenge of finding a reliable synthesis approach. Sol-gel route showed profitability in synthesizing such glasses with higher SnO₂ content [3,10,12]. Thus, in this work, we present a versatile and reliable sol-gel synthesis route to obtain transparent glass-ceramics with high content of SnO₂. We fabricated SiO₂-SnO₂ transparent glass ceramics as monoliths with a SnO₂ content up to 12.5 mol% and as planar waveguides with a SnO₂ content up to 30 mol%.

Fig. 1. Pictures of the densified SiO₂-SnO₂:Er³⁺ transparent glass-ceramics in forms of a) monoliths [15] and b) planar waveguides[7].

* Corresponding author: lam.tran@ifn.cnr.it

3 Enhanced photorefractivity

Attracted by potentials of SnO₂-doped glasses and glass-ceramics for applications in optical fibers and integrated photonics, numerous researches have investigated their photorefractivity. However, due to the low amount of SnO₂ content in the glass matrices (maximum up to 5 mol%), the reported UV-induced refractive index changes are limited to the order of 10⁻⁴[16]. In the last years, we have demonstrated: a) that we can fabricate SiO₂-SnO₂ transparent glass ceramics with high content of SnO₂ nanocrystals (from 20 to 30 mol%), and b) that those achieve highly efficient photorefractivity[16-18] (see Fig.2), sufficient for applying direct UV writing technique to fabricate channel waveguides and optical gratings. In such glass-ceramics, refractive index modification, induced by UV irradiation, is 4x10⁻³ [5,16-18] (see Fig.2). The fabrication of optical gratings on SiO₂:SnO₂:Er³⁺ glass-ceramics using UV direct writing technique is also recently realized [5]. It is worthy to note that the energy employed to write a grating on SiO₂:SnO₂:Er³⁺ glass-ceramics is much lower compared to those necessary to write the gratings on hydrogen loaded germanoborosilicate glasses [5].

Fig. 2. The refractive index change under UV irradiation of the sol-gel derived tin-dioxide-based glass-ceramics and the tin-doped silica glasses as a function of SnO₂ content[18].

4 Enhanced rare-earth luminescence

The low absorption cross section of the electronic states of the rare earth ions is an important drawback for their application in photonics. In this contest, employing luminescence sensitizers is a robust approach. As reported in our works on different rare-earth-activated SiO₂-SnO₂ glass-ceramic systems, e.g., monoliths, thin films, and waveguides [3-5,7,15-16], we have proved the role of SnO₂ nanocrystals as efficient rare-earth sensitizers. As an example, Figure 3a shows the excitation spectrum recorded at 1530 nm emission of Er³⁺ of a SiO₂-SnO₂:Er³⁺ glass-ceramic monoliths containing 10 mol% of SnO₂ and activated by 0.5 mol% Er³⁺. This spectrum demonstrates that when the glass-ceramic monolith is excited at SnO₂ bandgap centered at 360 nm, Er³⁺ luminescence is drastically enhanced in comparison with directly exciting at Er³⁺ electronic states, e.g., ²H_{11/2}, ⁴F_{7/2}, or ²F_{9/2}. Furthermore, in Figure 3b, the 1.5 μm emission spectrum

of Er³⁺ under SnO₂ bandgap excitation ($\lambda_{ex} = 360$ nm) reveals Stark splitting and narrow peaks. This again puts in evidence the location of Er³⁺ ions in SnO₂ crystalline local environment as well as the energy transfer from SnO₂ to the rare-earth ions[3,4,15].

Fig. 3. a) Excitation spectrum monitored at emission $\lambda_{em}=1530$ nm of Er³⁺ and b) emission spectrum under excitation at UV SnO₂ bandgap ($\lambda_{ex} = 360$ nm) using Edinburgh FLS980 spectrofluorometer of the SiO₂-SnO₂:Er³⁺ glass-ceramic monolith containing 10 mol% SnO₂ and activated by 0.5 mol% Er³⁺

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